

Structure and Reactivity. II¹. Dissociation Constants of α -Methyl- β -hydrogenarylidenesuccinates

V. W. JOSHI & G. BAGAVANT

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

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α -Methyl- β -hydrogenarylidenesuccinates² (Ia) have a carboxyl group in conjugation with an aromatic nucleus through an ethylenic linkage

and present a system suitable for studying the electronic effects of substituents transmitted through an ethylenic linkage. A series of half esters (Ia-Ar = (i) *p*-methoxy phenyl, (ii) *p*-methylphenyl, (iii) 3 : 4 methylenedioxyphenyl, (iv) 3 : 4 dimethoxyphenyl, (v) *m*-methylphenyl, (vi) phenyl, (vii) *m*-methoxyphenyl, (viii) *p*-chlorophenyl, (ix) *o*-methoxy phenyl) were prepared by the method El Abbady and El Assal³, the corresponding itaconic acids (Ib) were converted to their anhydrides and these cleaved with methanol, to yield the half ester (Ia). The dissociation constants were determined in 1 : 1-absolute alcohol-water (by volume) as it was the most suitable solvent and has been used by several workers^{4,5,6}. To a stirred mixture of α -methyl- β -hydrogen-*p*-methoxybenzylidenesuccinate (0.06265 g. in 25.0 ml alcohol) and 25.0 ml. solution of 3.6% potassium chloride (for constant ionic

Fig 1 α methyl β Hydrogen Arylidene Succinate
Temp 28.5 $\pm$ 0.2°C

strength) was added 10.0 ml. of 0.3218 *N* hydrochloric acid and this titrated against a standardized 0.5028 *N* sodium hydroxide solution (these solutions were made in 1:1-alcohol-water). The *pH* being determined (Elico-*pH* meter, Model No. LI-10) at every 0.2 ml. addition of alkali at a thermostatic temperature of $28.5 \pm 0.2^\circ$. The $\bar{n}$ value for each *pH* was calculated and the pK_a (5.35 ± 0.01) determined from the plot of $\bar{n}$ against *pH*. When the values were plotted against Hammett's σ values⁷ of the substituents, a linear relation is observed.

The *pK* values decrease with the decrease in the electron donating capacity of the substituent, in a manner similar to that of substituted benzoic acids⁴. This suggests that the electronic effect of the substituent is transmitted through in a quantitative measure to the β carboxyl of the itaconic acid system.

In the series of β -methyl- α -hydrogen arylidene succinates (Ic), prepared directly by Stobbe reaction of aldehydes and succinic esters with potassium tert. butoxide as catalyst⁸, the dissociation constants were determined in a manner similar to the above. It is observed that *pK* values vary over a very small range and are not significantly affected by the change in substituents in the aromatic nucleus.

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